
How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

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Project abstract:

How population in Canada is affected by Suicide from 1985 to 2010

Last modified: 22-04-2019

How population is affected by suicide in Canada 1985 - 2010 - Detailed DMP

1. Data summary

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

The purpose of data collection is to give accessibility to researchers to study previously recorded data by former researchers in the form of question answers. This useful to repeat and confirm the results.

It also helps to make predictions for future possibilities. so this project is mainly about how population is affected by suicide in Canada from 1985-2010.

the project has one objective is to show the correlation between suicide cases and the population rates in Canada.

used data Formats were in CSV either the collected or the generated, no existing data been re-used.

data were collected from datasets websites such as [Kaggle](#) and [Data.gov](#).

The size of expected data is less than 1 MB.

This data will be useful for students, researchers and who's intrested in mentioned topics.

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

The objective of this project is to find a correlation between population rate and suicide rate in Canada so in order to show this correlation we need to find a relation between the used datasets.

For example using year , country , population number and suicide number to make the visualization possible.

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

Plain text (.txt), Comma-separated values (.csv)

reasons why these formats were chosen :

1. can be opened or edited by text editors like notepad.
2. simple schema.
3. Importing CSV files can be much faster, and it also consumes less memory.
4. It's easy to programmatically manipulate CSV since, after all, they are simple text files. Using standardised or open formats ensures the long-term usability of data which are recommended for sharing and archiving.

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016 dataset compiled from datasets pulled from four other datasets linked by time and place, and was built to find signals correlated to increased suicide rates among different cohorts globally, across the socio-economic spectrum.

Population by Country (1980 - 2010) dataset published by National Renewable Energy Laboratory the methodology of data collecting was not mentioned.

data can be integrated with other data and be reused easily, also it can be preserved for a long term on Zenodo community.

In case of reusing the data no worries for any copy right issues or any other privacy issues because datasets are publicly available under the lincense of creative Commons cc Zero Lincense (cc-zero)

and Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Specify the origin of the data

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016 you can find it on [Kaggle](#) and Population by Country (1980 - 2010) you can find it on [Data.gov](#).

State the expected size of the data (if known)

Suicide Rates Overview 1985 to 2016 is about 396 KB and

Population by Country (1980 - 2010) is about 61 KB

and the output dataset is about 4 KB.

no need for additional storage costs, no challenges when sharing or transferring data between sites.

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

data is available at GitHub repository as an open source for code and other files related to this project also data is available on Zenodo.org

DOI: 10.5280/CanadaSuicide.data

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using DOI and Zenodo data is publicly available for everyone.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata [FAIR data]

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

for metadata about datasets please visit: <https://www.kaggle.com/russellyates88/suicide-rates-overview-1985-to-2016>

and

<https://catalog.data.gov/dataset/population-by-country-1980-2010>

for the results metadata please visit: <https://github.com/samihabakri/datasetExercise>

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Using DOI : Digital Object Identifier.

<https://doi.org/10.5280/CanadaSuicide.data>

Outline naming conventions used

Not mentioned.

Outline the approach towards search keyword

the approach of adding keywords is to help other researchers to find data and to make data reach a wider range of people.

Outline the approach for clear versioning

to show the correlation between the population and suicide rates in Canada as it is the objective of this project.

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

Not Mentioned.

2.2 Making data openly accessible [FAIR data]

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

All of the data is openly available.

Specify how the data will be made available

using GitHub repository , Zenodo.org and DOIs.

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

a text editor and python IDE to run the code.

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

GitHub repository: <https://github.com/samihabakri/datasetExercise>

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

Access is available under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

2.3 Making data interoperable [FAIR data]

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

N/A

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

N/A

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses) [FAIR data]

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

These Datasets are provided to you under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) and under a Creative Commons CCZero (cc-zero).

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

Data is available for no limits.

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

N/A

Describe data quality assurance processes

Completeness: The extent to which the expected data attributes are present.

Validity – Looks at whether the references are valid.

Accuracy – Data has to be accurate to be high quality.

availability – The extent of availability of the data.

Timeliness – Determines how up-to-date the data is in terms of the current task.

and finally Consistency.

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

No limits.

3. Allocation of resources

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

No Costs to make the Data FAIR because all the used tools and storage are for free.

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

design, develop, and implement data collection datasets.

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

No Costs.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

according to Zenodo available features data is stored safely for the future in the same cloud infrastructure as CERN's own LHC research data.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

N/A

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

N/A